

TABLE - SHOWING RECOVERIES OF FLUOMETURON IN FORTIFIED SAMPLES

Crops*	Fluometuron mg	added ppm	Average Fluometuron mg	found ppm	Average recovery percentage
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (cv. M.P. Chari)	0.25	0.50	0.24	0.48	96±3 [†]
	0.50	1.00	0.49	0.98	98±4
	1.0	2.00	0.97	1.94	97±4
	2.50	5.00	2.44	4.88	97±3
Maize fodder	0.25	0.50	0.23	0.46	92±5
	0.50	1.00	0.48	0.96	96±3
	1.00	2.00	0.96	0.96	96±3
	2.50	5.00	2.45	4.90	98±4
Sunflower fodder	0.25	0.50	0.24	0.48	96±4
	0.50	1.00	0.48	0.96	96±4
	1.00	2.00	0.98	1.96	98±3
	2.50	5.00	2.43	4.86	97±4
Wheat straw	0.25	0.50	0.24	0.48	96±3
	0.50	1.00	0.47	0.94	94±5
	1.00	2.00	0.97	4.97	97±4
	2.50	5.00	2.44	4.88	97±4
Soil	0.25	0.50	0.23	0.46	92±6
	0.50	1.00	0.47	0.94	94±4
	1.00	2.00	0.93	1.86	93±4
	2.50	5.00	2.44	4.84	97±4

* Five replicates of 50g each were analysed.

† Standard deviation.

A obtained as above on extraction and hydrolysis of the herbicide was estimated for its TFA content. The amount of TFA could be measured by plotting a graph of concentration of TFA against the optical density thereby calculating the amount of herbicide in the plant material (1 mg TFA = 1.44 mg fluometuron). The recoveries of fluometuron in fortified samples of fodder crops and soil have been shown in the table.

Alternate Procedure—The above method could be applied for the estimation of fluometuron to most of the leafy plant materials and seeds. Riden and Hopkins⁷ in one of the communications have reported that certain halogenated anilines sometimes form complexes with plant constituents and thus are not easily extracted with organic solvents. In such cases, the finely pulverized plant material (500-1000 g) was hydrolysed with aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (35%, 3 hrs) and 1 ml Dow corning antifoam under reflux at 170-175° in an oil bath. The hydrolysate was cooled in an ice bath and extracted with ether (400, 400, 200 ml) in a separating funnel. The combined ether extract was washed free of alkali dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to 150 ml. It was subsequently passed through a column (1.5×50 cm) of neutral alumina (40 g) in ether. The eluate was worked out as described above.

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Studies on Isoxazolones. Part IV. Formation Constants of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) Complexes of 3-Phenyl-5-Isoxazolone

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THE use of heterocyclic compounds like pyrazoles, imidazoles etc. and their substituted derivatives as complexing agents are abundant as found in literature¹⁻¹⁰. But there is neither any report on systematic

studies of oxazolone or isoxazolone class of compounds as ligands nor any information regarding stability-study of their metal complexes. However, a recent study on the metal complexes of dimethyl diisoxazolone has been reported from this laboratory¹¹.

The present paper describes the results of potentiometric determination of dissociation constant of a heterocyclic organic compound 3-phenyl-5-isoxazolone (R_pH) and the formation constants of its Cu(II) and $UO_2(II)$ complexes in (1 : 1) water-dioxan at a constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) at $31 \pm 0.5^\circ$ following Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{12,13}. The ligand R_pH may be represented in tautomeric forms as shown below :

Materials and Methods

The compound R_pH was prepared by condensation of ethyl benzoyl acetate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride following the method of Dains and Griffin¹⁴ and purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol and air-dried, m.p. 152° . R_pH forms brilliant red colour with Cu(II) and $UO_2(II)$ in (1 : 1) water-dioxan.

All other reagents were either of AR grade or properly purified. Their solutions were made in doubly distilled CO_2 -free water and purified dioxan¹⁵. Standard solutions were prepared as stated in an earlier communication¹⁶.

The measurements of pH values were made with a Cambridge pH -meter (Portable type) which was calibrated with aqueous buffer solutions. The electrode system consisted of a glass electrode (1-13 pH range) and SCE (as reference electrode) connected to the cell by means of an agar-2M $NaNO_3$ bridge.

Procedure :

Potentiometric titrations of 0.01M $HClO_4$ in (1 : 1) water-dioxan and of 0.05M R_pH containing 0.01M $HClO_4$ in (1 : 1) water-dioxan in the absence and in the presence of 0.01M or 0.005M $Cu(ClO_4)_2$ or $UO_2(ClO_4)_2$ with a standard NaOH solution in (1 : 1) water-dioxan were carried out at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) employing requisite amount of $NaClO_4$ and pH values were recorded in duplicate after the attainment of equilibrium at $31 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Results

Acid dissociation constant of the Ligand - R_pH :

The acid dissociation constant k^* of the ligand R_pH has been obtained by linear plot employing the equation (1)

$$pH = \log \frac{(1 - \bar{n}_H)}{\bar{n}_H} + pk^* \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{n}_H$ = the average number of proton bound to R_p^- ion. Standard deviation¹⁷ (σ) and limits of error have also been calculated¹⁸. Results are stated in Table 1.

Formation Constants of Metal complexes

The reaction between the ligand and the metal ion may be assumed to take place in a stepwise manner as stated by (2) and (3).

After attainment of equilibrium at any stage of titration it may be shown that

$$R_o = (R - P + F - H^+ + OH^-) \times k^* / [H^+] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } \bar{n}_R = \frac{1}{M} [R - (R - P + F - H^+ + OH^-)(1 + k^*/[(H^+)'])] \quad (5)$$

where M, R, F and P are initial concentrations of metal ion, ligand, free acid and alkali ; R_o , H^+ and OH^- are equilibrium concentrations of R_p^- , acid and alkali respectively, and $\bar{n}_R$ is the average number of ligand ion bound to metal ion.

In order to find the formation constants of metal complexes, the secondary concentration variable $\bar{n}_R$ may be described as

$$\bar{n}_R = \frac{K_1 R_o + 2K_1 K_2 R_o^2}{1 + K_1 R_o + K_1 K_2 R_o^2} \quad (6)$$

where K_1 and K_2 are 1st and 2nd step formation constants. After rearrangement, equation (6) may be written in the forms :

$$\frac{(2 - \bar{n}_R) R_o^2}{\bar{n}_R} = \frac{(\bar{n}_R - 1) R_o}{\bar{n}_R K_2} + \frac{1}{K_1 K_2} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{\bar{n}_R}{(1 - \bar{n}_R) R_o} = \frac{(2 - \bar{n}_R) R_o K_1 K_2}{(1 - \bar{n}_R)} + K_1 \quad (8)$$

In the case of Cu(II) complexes, $\log K_1$ and K_2 have been calculated from the intercept and slope of the straight line by plotting $(2 - \bar{n}_R) R_o^2 / \bar{n}_R$ against $(\bar{n}_R - 1) R_o / \bar{n}_R$ (equation 7). In the case of $UO_2(II)$ complexes, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ have been determined from the intercept and slope of the straight line by plotting $\bar{n}_R / (1 - \bar{n}_R) R_o$ against $(2 - \bar{n}_R) R_o / (1 - \bar{n}_R)$ (equation 8). Using the experimentally determined values of K_1 and K_2 , calculated $\bar{n}_R$ values have been found out by equation (6). Standard deviation (σ) and limits of error have also been calculated. Results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE I—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF R_pH AND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Ligand	pk*	Metal (II)	log K_1	log K_2	Standard deviation (Range)
R_pH	5.04 ± 0.02	Cu(II)	2.01 ± 0.03	1.57 ± 0.03	$\pm 0.013 (0.01 < \bar{n}_R < 1.10)$
	$[\sigma = \pm 0.009 (0.3 < \bar{n}_H < 1.0)]$	UO ₂ (II)	3.62 ± 0.05	3.20 ± 0.05	$\pm 0.022 (0.20 < \bar{n}_H < 0.80)$

Discussion

The potentiometric study in mixed solvents was made following the procedure developed by Van Uitert and Hass¹⁹. Acid concentration (h) of any water-dioxan mixture was determined by graphical extrapolation^{20,21} of plot of pH value against (-log h).

The pk* value of the ligand R_pH indicates that it is a weak acid. During titration of Cu(II) in presence of R_pH (being in large excess) with NaOH solution, $\bar{n}_R$ could not be obtained beyond 1.3 due to earlier precipitation. The stability constant data indicate that the stability order is UO₂(II) > Cu(II). Formation curves were obtained on plotting $\bar{n}_{RCalc}$ and $\bar{n}_{R(Exp)}$ values against corresponding p_{RD} values. The experimental curve is in good agreement with the calculated one within the region $0.01 < \bar{n}_R < 1.10$ and $0.2 < \bar{n}_R < 0.80$ in the cases of Cu(II) and UO₂(II) complexes respectively. In dilute solution, the experimental formation curve of UO₂(II) complex agrees well with the calculated curve upto $\bar{n}_R$ value equal to 1.15. Deviations of the experimental formation curve from the calculated one outside these regions indicate that the course of reaction at the later stages of complex formation (pH > 5) may be somewhat different from these represented by equations (2) and (3). The formation of polynuclear complexes of UO₂(II) is not completely ruled out at the later stages of complex formation.

By potentiometric titration of R_pH in presence of Ni(II) and Co(II), the formation of complex compounds of Ni(II) and Co(II) is not indicated.

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Synthesis and Reactions of 4-Picolyl Magnesium Iodide

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4-Picolyl magnesium iodide(I) was prepared by reacting ethyl magnesium iodide with 4-picoline in connection with the synthesis of 6,7-(4', 5'-pyrido)-morphans. The structure of I was proved by its reactions with benzaldehyde and acetone when 1-(pyridyl-4)-2-phenyl ethanol-2 (II) and 1-(pyridyl-4)-2-methyl-propanol-2 (III) were obtained.

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